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2 **CartoScope: democratized, harmonized, and scalable**
3 **ecosystem for subcellular spatial omics exploration**

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20 **Abstract**

21 Subcellular spatial omics technologies now generate vast datasets that capture tissue organization
22 at microscopic resolution. However, biological discovery has lagged behind data production due
23 to fragmentation across platforms, reliance on binning or imperfect cell segmentation, and high
24 computational barriers that limit accessibility for experimental biologists. Here we present
25 CartoScope for democratized, scalable, and segmentation-independent exploration and analysis
26 of subcellular omics data. CartoScope efficiently renders multi-resolution spatial omics data on
27 demand through an interactive web interface, enabling multi-layered visualization of genes,
28 transcriptional programs, and inferred cell types over histological images at molecular resolution.
29 Beyond visualization, CartoScope supports interactive analysis of user-defined regions-of-
30 interest (ROIs), including region-specific cell type composition analysis and differential gene
31 expression analyses stratified by cell type or spatial context. The CartoScope ecosystem
32 integrates a backend harmonization pipeline and a public data repository, currently hosting over
33 320 datasets spanning 16 technologies and 28 tissue types, with an architecture designed for
34 continuous expansion and scalable integration of future datasets. Through representative
35 applications, including cross-technology benchmarking and cellular, subcellular, and
36 multicellular analysis of transcriptomic heterogeneity across development and disease, we
37 demonstrate that CartoScope enables rapid biological discovery, hypothesis testing, and insight
38 sharing within minutes of web-based operation.

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40 **Introduction**

41 Spatial transcriptomics (ST) and proteomics technologies have transformed the study of tissue
42 biology by enabling the measurement of individual molecules while preserving spatial context ¹.
43 Early ST methods offered multicellular resolution (10-100 μm /spot), revealing broad spatial
44 patterns of transcription across tissues. More recently, advances in both sequencing-based and
45 imaging-based approaches have pushed spatial resolution to subcellular scale, giving rise to
46 microscopic-resolution spatial transcriptomics (μST) ². These technologies now allow systematic
47 interrogation of molecular organization within complex tissues, offering unprecedented
48 opportunities to study tissue architecture, cell state heterogeneity, developmental processes, and
49 disease-associated remodeling in situ.

50 The rapid evolution of subcellular omics technologies, particularly μST , has led to an explosion
51 of datasets generated by individual laboratories and large-scale consortia. These datasets span
52 diverse experimental platforms, spatial resolutions, tissue types, and biological conditions,
53 collectively encoding rich information about cellular composition, spatial organization, and
54 functional states. As summarized in recent reviews ^{1,2}, μST has the potential to bridge molecular
55 profiling with histology, linking transcriptional programs to tissue morphology and physiology at
56 previously inaccessible scales. However, despite these advances in technology and data
57 acquisition, the pace of biological discovery has somewhat remained modest relative to the
58 volume and quality of data being produced.

59 Several interconnected challenges have limited the effective use of μST data ². First, μST
60 datasets are intrinsically fragmented due to technological heterogeneity. Sequencing-based and
61 imaging-based platforms differ substantially in spatial sampling, signal characteristics, and data

62 structures, leading to disparate preprocessing strategies such as grid-based binning or image-
63 derived segmentation. As a result, no unified framework has been established for parallel and
64 harmonized analysis across technologies. Second, most existing analytical pipelines rely on
65 binning or cell segmentation, approaches that either obscure fine-grained spatial information or
66 depend on imperfect boundary inference, resulting in signal contamination, data loss, and
67 reduced sensitivity to subcellular or continuous spatial patterns³. Although segmentation-free
68 and multi-modal segmentation approaches have begun to address these limitations⁴, there is
69 currently no large-scale resource or cross-platform analysis pipeline that systematically resolves
70 the fragmentation across μ ST technologies at a scale comparable to efforts in the single-cell and
71 lower-resolution ST communities, such as cellxgene⁵ and the Human Cell Atlas⁶.

72 Finally, the scale and complexity of subcellular omics data pose substantial barriers to
73 accessibility. Raw spatial sequencing and/or imaging data are publicly available through
74 repositories such as Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO), Sequence Read Archive (SRA), and
75 Zenodo, yet meaningful exploration of these resources typically requires advanced
76 computational expertise and access to high-performance computing infrastructure. Consequently,
77 many biologists and biomedical researchers, who are central to hypothesis generation and
78 biological interpretation, are largely sidelined from direct interaction with μ ST datasets. This
79 disconnect between data production and interpretation represents a major bottleneck in
80 translating μ ST technologies into broader biological insights.

81 To overcome these limitations, a paradigm shift is required in how μ ST data are accessed,
82 explored, and analyzed. Rather than treating each dataset as a monolithic object that must be
83 fully downloaded, processed, and segmented prior to interrogation, μ ST data can instead be
84 viewed as spatial information layers that can be queried dynamically according to scientific

85 intent. Geographic information systems (GIS) provide a useful analogy: modern map platforms
86 enable interactive exploration of massive, multi-scale spatial datasets by delivering only the
87 information required for a given view or region of interest. Users can seamlessly navigate across
88 scales, define regions, overlay contextual features, and perform location-specific queries without
89 direct exposure to underlying data complexity or computational infrastructure.

90 Inspired by this paradigm, we reasoned that μ ST data could be organized within a multi-
91 resolution, query-driven framework in which histological images serve as the spatial substrate
92 and molecular measurements are treated as layered annotations. Such an approach would allow
93 biologists to interactively explore tissues at microscopic submicron-scale pixel resolution, define
94 regions of interest, compare spatial domains, and perform region-specific and cell-type-specific
95 analyses without reliance on binning or explicit cell segmentation. This perspective motivated
96 the development of CartoScope, a GIS-inspired visualization and analysis platform designed to
97 unify heterogeneous μ ST technologies, preserve fine-grained spatial information, and
98 substantially lower the barrier to data exploration and biological discoveries.

99 In this study, we present CartoScope as an integrated ecosystem for segmentation-independent
100 exploration and analysis of microscopic-resolution spatial transcriptomics data. We describe the
101 design principles and implementation of its three core components: CartLoader, a backend
102 pipeline for harmonizing diverse μ ST datasets; CartoStore, a public repository hosting uniformly
103 processed μ ST datasets; and CartoScope, a web-based interface enabling interactive visualization
104 and region-aware analysis at molecular resolution. We then demonstrate the utility of
105 CartoScope through a series of representative applications, including cross-technology
106 benchmarking, resolution of cellular and subcellular transcriptomic heterogeneity, and region-
107 and context-specific analyses across development, normal physiology, and disease. Together,

108 these examples illustrate how CartoScope bridges the gap between μ ST data generation and
109 biological discovery by enabling rapid, intuitive, and scalable web-based exploration.

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115 **Results**

116 **CartoScope ecosystem for harmonized analysis of microscopic-resolution spatial omics**

117 We developed CartoScope as an integrated ecosystem for harmonized processing, analysis,
118 visualization, and sharing of microscopic-resolution spatial omics (μ ST) data across
119 technologies. The ecosystem consists of three tightly coupled components: CartLoader, a
120 backend pipeline that harmonizes raw platform outputs and performs segmentation-independent
121 pixel-level inference; CartoStore, a cloud-native repository for hosting processed datasets and
122 associated metadata; and CartoScope, a web-based application for interactive visualization and
123 region-based analysis (Fig. 1A). This modular architecture decouples data processing and
124 analysis from user-facing exploration, enabling investigators to interactively examine μ ST data
125 without local preprocessing or programming expertise. Users can also process their own μ ST
126 datasets and upload them to Zenodo, Amazon S3, or any other Cross-Origin Resource Sharing
127 (CORS)-supporting cloud storage, allowing them be shared and explored inside the CartoScope
128 ecosystem.

129 A central design principle of the ecosystem is to treat μ ST datasets as spatially indexed and
130 pyramidally tiled layers that can be queried dynamically by location and scale, rather than as
131 monolithic files requiring full download, binning, or cell segmentation. To support interactive
132 navigation from tissue-scale views to micron-scale molecular detail, the ecosystem streams only
133 the subset of data required for the current viewport or user-defined region of interest (ROI). This
134 design preserves native spatial resolution, enables rapid hypothesis generation, and supports
135 interoperability across heterogeneous technologies.

136 **Cross-platform harmonization and molecular-resolution inference using FICTURE2**

137 CartLoader is a modular, reproducible backend pipeline that converts raw spatial omics outputs
138 from diverse sequencing-based and imaging-based microscopic-resolution spatial
139 transcriptomics (μ ST) platforms into a harmonized, analysis-ready representation optimized for
140 cloud-based querying and visualization. For each dataset, CartLoader standardizes molecular
141 readouts into a common spatial coordinate system expressed in microns, with explicit gene or
142 feature identifiers. Optional platform-specific attributes, including quality-control metrics, z-
143 coordinates, and cell or segmentation metadata, are retained as auxiliary features while ensuring
144 compatibility with downstream analyses and interoperability with existing toolchains.

145 A central component of CartLoader is the integration of FICTURE2 as the default engine for
146 segmentation-independent pixel-level analysis. Following harmonization of raw molecular
147 coordinates, CartLoader invokes FICTURE2 to perform spatial inference directly at the
148 molecular or pixel level, without requiring prior cell segmentation or grid-based binning. This
149 segmentation-independent analysis strategy is applicable across all known high-resolution spatial
150 omics technologies, including imaging-based and sequencing-based μ ST platforms, as well as
151 imaging- and sequencing-based subcellular spatial proteomics assays. By avoiding reliance on
152 cell boundaries inferred from histological images, FICTURE2 enables uniform processing of
153 datasets regardless of whether or not reliable segmentation information is available.

154 This design addresses a fundamental limitation of current subcellular spatial omics analysis
155 pipelines, as no general-purpose segmentation algorithm performs robustly across heterogeneous
156 tissues, tissue preparation protocols, and imaging modalities. In practice, segmentation is often
157 compromised by variable tissue morphology, crowded or multinucleated cells, two-dimensional

158 sectioning artifacts, or suboptimal histological image quality ². By integrating FICTURE2 into
159 CartLoader, all subcellular spatial omics datasets can be processed through a unified and
160 harmonized pipeline without compromising its original resolution, independent of segmentation
161 quality or availability. When segmentation boundaries and cell-type annotations are provided by
162 platform-specific software or external tools, CartLoader can also ingest these results and make
163 them available alongside pixel-level inference. This allows both segmentation-based and
164 segmentation-independent analyses to coexist within the same framework.

165 To ensure practical usability at scale, FICTURE2 was designed to be highly computationally
166 efficient, achieving an order-of-magnitude speedup over the original FICTURE implementation
167 ⁷, which itself was already substantially faster than existing pixel-level spatial inference methods
168 ^{8,9}. This efficiency allows CartLoader to process many high-content datasets containing hundreds
169 of millions to billions of molecules without introducing computational bottlenecks, enabling
170 routine harmonization and analysis of large public collections and multi-sample studies within
171 the CartoScope ecosystem.

172 **Cloud-optimized multi-resolution representation of raw and inferred spatial layers**

173 Following harmonization and pixel-level inference, CartLoader encodes raw molecular data,
174 inferred spatial factors, and optional cell-based analysis results into a multi-resolution, spatially
175 indexed representation using PMTiles, a cloud-optimized geospatial tiling format. Molecular
176 readouts and pixel-level inference results are stored as vector tiles, whereas histological and
177 auxiliary imaging modalities (for example H&E, DAPI, polyT, or antibody staining) are stored
178 as raster tiles. All layers share a common coordinate system and pyramid structure, ensuring
179 precise spatial alignment across modalities.

180 The PMTiles representation enables efficient random access through HTTP range requests,
181 allowing downstream applications to retrieve only the spatial tiles required for a given zoom
182 level or ROI. Lower-resolution pyramid levels store aggregated or subsampled representations,
183 enabling smooth navigation across scales, whereas higher-resolution levels preserve molecular or
184 pixel-level detail. Importantly, inferred spatial factors from FICTURE2 are embedded directly
185 within the tiled representation as per-molecule or per-pixel annotations, allowing them to be
186 visualized, queried, and summarized in the same manner as primary molecular signals.

187 CartLoader also generates structured metadata describing processing parameters, inference
188 settings, gene loadings, and quality-control summaries. These metadata are stored alongside tiled
189 data and exposed through standardized interfaces, enabling reproducibility and transparent
190 provenance tracking.

191 **CartoStore democratizes access to harmonized public datasets and analysis outputs**

192 CartoStore serves as the primary data distribution layer of the ecosystem, hosting CartLoader-
193 processed datasets together with their associated metadata and analysis results. Datasets are
194 stored in cloud object storage with Cross-Origin Resource Sharing (CORS)-enabled access,
195 allowing CartoScope and other clients to stream tiled data directly without intermediate servers.
196 This architecture supports scalable access by a large number of users while minimizing storage
197 duplication and egress overhead.

198 CartoStore is a freely accessible Amazon Simple Storage Service (S3) repository, supported by
199 the AWS Open Data Sponsorship Program, designed to host publicly available μ ST datasets at
200 scale. The CartoStore architecture is extensible, supporting hosting backends like AWS S3 and
201 other object stores, such as Google Cloud Storage (GCS), as well as public repositories that

202 permits CORS access, such as Zenodo. By enforcing a standardized dataset layout and metadata
203 schema, CartoStore enables immediate interoperability across studies and technologies,
204 providing a consistent foundation for comparative analysis, benchmarking, and method
205 development.

206 **Depth and breadth of spatial omics coverage in CartoStore**

207 CartoStore currently hosts 320 spatial omics datasets encompassing 34.7 billion transcripts/
208 proteins measured across 16 different technologies, reflecting substantial depth and breadth
209 across biological systems, disease contexts, and spatial profiling technologies. The collection is
210 dominated by human and mouse datasets, providing strong coverage for both clinical and
211 experimental studies, while also incorporating additional model organisms and plant systems,
212 including Arabidopsis, rhesus macaque, soybean, and zebrafish. This multi-organism
213 representation supports cross-species comparisons and methodological validation across diverse
214 biological settings.

215 The hosted datasets span a wide range of tissue types, with a particular focus on brain, pancreas,
216 colon, breast, lung, prostate, kidney, liver, and ovary. They also include developmental and
217 immune-related samples such as whole embryos, lymph nodes, tonsils, and spleen. This
218 extensive tissue coverage enables analyses ranging from organ-specific cellular organization to
219 comparative studies across tissue systems and developmental stages.

220 CartoStore includes datasets derived from both normal physiology and a broad spectrum of
221 disease contexts. In addition to healthy reference tissues, the repository contains extensive cancer
222 datasets, inflammatory and immune-mediated diseases such as Crohn's disease and ulcerative
223 colitis, renal and pulmonary pathologies, and genetically defined or experimentally engineered

224 disease models, including neurodegenerative and mitochondrial mutation models and xenograft
225 systems. This diversity supports systematic comparison between healthy and diseased tissues
226 across multiple spatial modalities.

227 The CartoScope ecosystem is explicitly technology-agnostic and supports a broad array of spatial
228 profiling technologies. It requires only transcripts and their spatial coordinates as the minimum
229 input. CartoStore hosts sequencing-based and imaging-based transcriptomic datasets, spatial
230 proteomic measurements, and emerging multi-omics data. Supported commercial platforms
231 include Xenium¹⁰, Visium HD¹¹, MERFISH¹², CosMx-SMI¹³, Salus-STS¹⁴, and Stereo-seq¹⁵.
232 In parallel, CartoStore integrates datasets generated using academic and open methodologies,
233 including Seq-Scope¹⁶, Open-ST¹⁷, Nova-ST¹⁸, Pixel-seq¹⁹, STARmap PLUS²⁰, and
234 seqFISH+²¹. Proteomic technologies such as Seq-Scope-X²² and CODEX²³ are also supported,
235 together with recently released multi-omic Xenium²⁴ and Singular G4X²⁵ platforms. By
236 harmonizing these heterogeneous data types within a unified data model, CartoStore enables
237 direct cross-technology comparison and promotes integrative spatial analyses.

238 Crucially, the high efficiency of the CartLoader processing pipeline makes it feasible to host not
239 only the current corpus of public spatial omics datasets but also anticipated future datasets at
240 similar or larger scale. In line with this goal, we are actively working toward hosting all high-
241 resolution spatial omics datasets currently available in the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO),
242 further expanding coverage and ensuring comprehensive access to public spatial data. This
243 scalability, combined with broad biological and technological coverage, establishes CartoStore
244 as a comprehensive and extensible foundation for large-scale spatial omics data sharing,
245 exploration, and method development.

246 **CartoScope provides interactive visualization and ROI-based analysis of raw and inferred**
247 **layers**

248 CartoScope is a web-based application that enables interactive exploration of harmonized μ ST
249 datasets processed by CartLoader and hosted in CartoStore. Using a map-style interface, users
250 can pan and zoom across tissue sections while dynamically toggling synchronized layers,
251 including histological images, gene-level molecular distributions, default pixel-level spatial
252 factors inferred by FICTURE2, and optional factors inferred by additional algorithms such as
253 segmentation-based cell type clustering. Because CartoScope streams multi-resolution pyramidal
254 tiles on demand, it supports responsive visualization of large tissue areas while preserving
255 micron-scale detail.

256 CartoScope further links visualization to analysis by supporting user-defined ROI interrogation.
257 Users can define arbitrary ROIs and compute region-specific summaries, including enrichment
258 of genes or spatial factors, comparisons between ROIs, and conditional analyses stratified by
259 inferred transcriptional programs or optional cell-based annotations. These operations leverage
260 the same tiled representation generated by CartLoader, ensuring consistency between
261 visualization and analysis. For downstream rigor and reproducibility, CartoScope supports export
262 of ROI-defined data and annotations into commonly used formats for offline analysis with
263 established single-cell and spatial omics toolchains.

264 **Sharing spatial analysis views and settings through reproducible bookmarks**

265 A key feature of CartoScope is the ability to generate a persistent bookmark link at any stage of
266 web-based exploration. This link captures the complete analytical state of the session, including
267 the current field of view, selected visualization layers, factor display settings, gene plots, ROI

268 definitions, and associated analysis parameters, together with the underlying dataset reference.
269 The bookmark is provided as a standard HTTP URL and can be saved within a user account for
270 future access.

271 Bookmark links can be readily shared with collaborators, enabling precise communication of
272 analytical context without the need for manual recreation of views or parameter settings.
273 Importantly, these links can also be disseminated publicly, including in social media or formal
274 publications. Readers can directly access the exact spatial view and analytical configuration used
275 by the investigator, facilitating transparent reporting, reproducibility, and independent
276 exploration of the same dataset.

277 In the sections below, we present representative use cases that illustrate how CartoScope
278 supports user-driven benchmarking, cellular and subcellular factor analysis, and investigation of
279 biological processes including eye development, intratumoral heterogeneity, and bone formation
280 in the growth plate. All display panels, except schematic diagrams, were generated directly from
281 CartoScope screenshots without post hoc modification. Corresponding bookmark links are
282 provided in the figure legends, allowing readers to reproduce each view and extend the analyses
283 further. Through this mechanism, CartoScope promotes interactive dissemination of spatial
284 omics analyses and encourages the generation of new hypotheses grounded in shared, navigable
285 data contexts.

286 **CartoScope enables user-defined benchmarking across various datasets**

287 With the depth and variety of datasets available in the CartoStore ecosystem, users have access
288 to datasets produced by a wide range of spatial technologies without the barrier of computational
289 expertise, access to high-performance computing environments, or the time and resources

290 required for data preprocessing and custom analyses. Brain is the most frequently analyzed tissue
291 among available spatial datasets, and among different anatomical regions, the hippocampus is the
292 most intensively studied. Across the 16 technologies currently featured in CartoScope, brain
293 datasets are available for the majority of platforms, enabling direct cross-technology
294 comparisons within a common tissue context.

295 By default, CartoScope displays basic statistics for each dataset, including analyzed tissue area
296 and dimensions, the number of examined gene features, and the number of detected unique
297 transcript counts, providing users with an immediate overview of dataset scale, coverage, and
298 depth (Fig. 1B). By opening individual datasets and plotting genes of interest, users can further
299 evaluate gene coverage, detection depth, and overall suitability for their specific analytical
300 purposes.

301 As an example, we examined hippocampal datasets using well-characterized dentate gyrus (DG)
302 markers, *Prox1* and *Dcx1*. *Prox1* is a general marker for DG granule neurons, whereas *Dcx1* is
303 more restricted to neural progenitors. Spatial plotting of *Prox1* and *Dcx1*, together with the
304 meningeal fibroblast marker *Ptgds*, revealed clear DG morphology in many datasets containing
305 these genes (Fig. 1C). These included targeted approaches with large gene panels, such as
306 Xenium Prime and probe-based Visium HD, as well as untargeted sequencing-based approaches,
307 including Visium HD (3'-mRNA), Stereo-seq, Salus-STS, Seq-Scope, and its derivatives. In
308 contrast, some targeted imaging-based datasets, such as MERFISH and CosMx SMI, did not
309 include these genes, and STARmap PLUS datasets contained *Prox1* and *Ptgds* but not *Dcx1*.

310 Gene-level visualization also intuitively revealed characteristic differences between
311 technologies. Probe-based methods, such as Xenium Prime, STARmap PLUS, and probe-based

312 Visium HD, showed higher apparent molecular counts with greater spatial precision, reflecting
313 their strength in characterizing targeted species. In contrast, untargeted Visium HD and Seq-
314 Scope-based methods showed fewer detected molecules per gene, resulting in sparser patterns
315 for individual molecular species (Fig. 1C), even though their total molecular capture was
316 comparable to targeted approaches and they measured a substantially larger number of genes
317 (Fig. 1B). Stereo-seq showed moderately denser molecular detection than other sequencing-
318 based methods, whereas Salus-STS exhibited highly dense detection comparable to probe-based
319 approaches (Fig. 1C), consistent with reports of markedly higher capture efficiency¹⁴. However,
320 Salus-STS also showed increased diffusion and background relative to targeted methods.

321 For genes with highly abundant mRNA expression, targeted imaging-based approaches often fail
322 because dense molecular arrangements can interfere with demultiplexing. For example, *Ttr*, a
323 canonical marker of the choroid plexus, was not included in most probe-based imaging datasets,
324 with the exception of probe-based Visium HD, which relies on sequencing rather than
325 multiplexed imaging. Therefore, all sequencing-based methods, but not imaging-based methods,
326 robustly captured the spatially restricted, high-level expression of *Ttr* (Fig. 1D).

327 Targeted approaches also have an inherent limitation in the number of genes measured, which
328 can result in missing biologically important gene species. To illustrate this, we examined genes
329 specifically expressed in CA2 neurons, a small subregion of the hippocampal cornu ammonis
330 (CA) that functions as a critical hub for social memory²⁶. Representative CA2 markers,
331 including *Ptpn5*, *Pcp4*, and *Rgs14*²⁷, were present in all sequencing-based datasets but were
332 absent from most imaging-based datasets, with the only exception of CosMx SMI, which
333 included *Pcp4* in its probe set. All sequencing-based approaches clearly captured CA2-restricted

334 expression of these genes (Fig. 1E), which localized to the junction between CA1 and CA3
335 spatial factors.

336 Notably, even in datasets lacking these canonical CA2 markers, region-of-interest (ROI)-based
337 differential expression analysis successfully identified CA2-enriched genes. For example,
338 although Xenium Prime and MERFISH datasets did not include *Ptpn5*, *Pcp4*, or *Rgs14*, ROI-
339 based analysis identified alternative CA2-associated genes, some of which were not sensitively
340 detected by sequencing-based methods (Fig. 1F). One such example was *Lgr5*, a well-
341 characterized stem and progenitor cell marker, which showed unexpected enrichment in the CA2
342 region in a MERFISH dataset (Fig. 1F), an observation not seen in other platforms.

343 Similar tissue-specific benchmarking could be done for tissues that were examined across
344 various technologies such as testes, which was examined by three representative sequencing-
345 based technologies including Seq-Scope, Stereo-Seq and Salus-STS (Fig. S1A), and mouse and
346 human kidneys (Fig. S1B–D), profiled by Probe-based Visium HD and Xenium, untargeted
347 Stereo-Seq, and targeted imaging-based SeqFISH+.

348 Together, these examples demonstrate how CartoScope enables user-specified benchmarking
349 across datasets and technologies, allowing users to evaluate dataset suitability for their specific
350 biological questions and, in some cases, identify novel region-specific gene signatures. For
351 biological investigators seeking to rapidly explore expression patterns of specific genes or gene
352 sets, or to identify genes enriched in defined anatomical regions, these analyses can be performed
353 within minutes. For computational investigators, CartoScope provides an efficient way to assess
354 dataset breadth, depth, and quality before investing effort in data download and preprocessing.
355 Importantly, CartoScope also allows users to download subsets of data based on user-defined

356 ROIs, substantially reducing data transfer size and computational burden for downstream custom
357 analyses.

358 **Integrative interpretation of spatial gene expression using CartoScope and FICTURE2**

359 CartoScope can visualize both segmentation-based cell type clustering (when provided from the
360 dataset) and segmentation-independent pixel-level transcriptome factor assignment. CartoScope
361 can also show pixel-level projection of the segmentation-based clustering results, and support
362 spatial gene plotting in raw scale while preserving the original resolution. These complementary
363 layers of information substantially improve the interpretability of μ ST data.

364 When available, cell-based clustering analysis often provides straightforward interpretation of
365 spatial transcriptome at single cell resolution and is widely considered as the *de facto* standard.
366 On the other hand, segmentation-independent pixel-level inference, offered by FICTURE2, is
367 particularly useful when cell segmentation is unreliable or infeasible. The unsupervised Latent
368 Dirichlet Analysis (LDA) factors inferred by FICTURE2 represents cell types or more fine-
369 grained transcriptional programs of co-expressed genes ²⁸, thus providing a complementary view
370 to interpretations based on segmented cells.

371 In an example of Xenium human pancreatic islet where accurate cell segmentation is
372 challenging, the default Xenium Ranger analysis, performed based on DAPI-based cell
373 segmentation, was not able to distinguish transcripts from various cells in a crowded spatial area.
374 As a result, Xenium Ranger clustering failed to distinguish various pancreatic islet cell types
375 from segmented cell transcriptome (Fig. 2A). Similarly, the islet subtypes were not isolated when
376 using our LDA-based cell clustering algorithm (Fig. 2B). However, when we used pixel-level
377 inference of FICTURE2 (Fig. 2C–F), we were able to identify all 5 known types of pancreatic

378 islets (alpha, beta, gamma, delta and epsilon cells, expressing *GCG*, *INS*, *PPY*, *SST* and *GHRL*,
379 respectively), as well as a recently identified CPHN cells²⁹ with high *CHGA* expression with
380 low hormone expression (Fig. 2G–L). Using CartoScope gene plotting function, it is easy to
381 inspect that these six cell types correlate well with their corresponding marker genes (Fig. 2M–
382 R). Additional genes enriched for these factors, identifiable through factor description in
383 CartoScope, may further support cell type identity and function. For instance, *PCSK2*, which
384 encodes a prohormone convertase involved in proinsulin processing, was highly enriched in the
385 *INS*-expressing beta cell cluster.

386 Similar results were obtained from two independent CosMx SMI datasets on normal human
387 pancreas. For one of the datasets, the Spatial Touchstone dataset³⁰ covering 1,000 genes, the
388 gene panel only had three hormones: *INS*, *GCG* and *SST*; but the FICTURE factorization was
389 able to detect all these three islet types (beta, alpha and delta, correspondingly), which was not
390 detected from cell segmentation methods (Fig. S2A–F). The factorization results (Fig. S2D–F)
391 were consistent with the expression of these hormonal markers (Fig. S2G–I). Another dataset
392 generated by Nanostring (with 18,996 genes), examined two very small regions; here again cell
393 segmentation only detected islet types without their subtypes (Fig. S2J–K). Likely because of the
394 small sample area, FICTURE2 detected only the three major islet types (beta, alpha and delta;
395 Fig. S2L–N). But gene plotting of all five hormones was sufficient to reveal the location of all
396 five known pancreatic islet subtypes in the dataset (Fig. S2O).

397 The utility of visualizing cell segmentation, FICTURE2 factorization, and gene plotting in one
398 platform could be also exemplified by examining a recent dataset which show the prevalence of
399 cell senescence during skin wound healing process³¹. Default Xenium cell clustering was able to
400 reveal various cell types relevant for skin wound healing; however, their spatial visualization was

401 less than ideal and does not show fine organization corresponding to skin histology (Fig. 2S).
402 CartoScope supports pixel-level projection of the pre-learned cell types/factors, implemented in
403 FICTURE2, and such projection clearly revealed histological layers and architectures of skin
404 wound healing much more clearly (Fig. 2T) when compared to the original segmentation (Fig.
405 2S). Furthermore, CartoScope performs gene plotting on the segmentation or pixel-level
406 projection background, allowing us to inspect which cell type(s) express the plotted genes. Gene
407 plotting of the representative senescence marker p21 (*CDKN1A*, cyan) and p16 (*CDKN2A*, red)
408 clearly visualizes that wounding induces both p21 and p16 (Fig. 2U–V), and that p21 is highly
409 induced in injury-responding keratinocytes and skeletal muscle populations while p16 is more
410 prominently upregulated in wound-associated myofibroblasts (Fig. 2V–W). These observations
411 highlight the precision and utility of harmonized analysis in CartoScope.

412 **Harmonized and adaptable analysis of lymphoid organ spatial transcriptome**

413 Lymphoid organs, including the tonsil, lymph node, and spleen, are highly organized immune
414 tissues that coordinate antigen recognition, lymphocyte activation, and the generation of adaptive
415 immune responses. These organs contain spatially distinct microenvironments, such as B cell
416 follicles, germinal centers, T cell zones, and specialized stromal niches, which support tightly
417 regulated cellular interactions. Their structural complexity and functional compartmentalization
418 make them well suited for investigation using spatially resolved transcriptomic and multiomic
419 technologies; and correspondingly, a number of public datasets from μ ST technology are
420 available. However, it has been difficult to examine them in the same harmonized platform to
421 infer transcriptional programs at pixel-level resolution.

422 CartoScope streamlines the process by hosting publicly available lymphoid organ datasets from
423 both human and mouse. Many of datasets, such as Visium HD data from human tonsil (Fig.
424 S3A), do not have histology-based segmentation information; however, FICTURE2 factor
425 inference allowed understanding spatial pattern of gene expression and cell types, which
426 correlated well with its underlying histology (Fig. S3A). When the segmentation information is
427 available and cell type was previously detected and annotated, CartoScope allows users to
428 browse them in the exact same platform with aligned histology (Fig. S3B–E) while also
429 providing pixel-level FICTURE2 projections of those previously annotated cell types into raw
430 resolution (Fig. S3B,D,E).

431 In addition to transcriptome data, CartoScope is also capable of processing and analyzing and
432 high-resolution spatial proteomics data, based on digital sequence tag detection, such as done in
433 recent Seq-Scope-X datasets simultaneously profiling 100-150 antibodies²². Through the same
434 FICTURE2 analysis pipeline, spatial factors of mouse spleen (Fig. S3F) and human tonsil (Fig.
435 S3G) datasets were successfully detected and visualized, even though there are no matching
436 histology or segmentation information. CODEX²³ is another platform that performs high-
437 resolution spatial proteomics through multiplexed imaging of ~37 antibodies. By converting
438 fluorescence images into digital expression count matrix, we were able to conduct the analysis
439 using the same FICTURE2 pipeline and can detect cellular and subcellular factors from human
440 lymph node (Fig. S3H) and spleen (Fig. S3I) datasets, which reveal fine structural details of
441 different cell types and cell compartments (e.g. nucleus and membrane) expressing different
442 proteins. CartoScope browser also supports browsing of original fluorescence staining results in
443 all imaging-based proteomic datasets, as exemplified in the case of the recent G4X dataset,
444 which harbored both transcriptomic (Fig. S3J,K) and proteomic (Fig. S3L) information, where

445 transcriptomic datasets were analyzed as done for the other datasets while proteomic data could
446 be displayed individually as images. Therefore, CartoScope provides flexibility where it can
447 process protein imaging data as a digital matrix (for multi-modal analysis) or fluorescence image
448 (for cell type inspection and verification) and visualize to users in an adaptable way.

449 **Comprehensive analysis of spatial transcriptome during lens development**

450 Lens development is characterized by a unique differentiation program in which epithelial cells
451 at the lens equator elongate and progressively mature into highly specialized fiber cells. During
452 this process, differentiating fiber cells undergo organelle degradation, including the loss of
453 nuclei, mitochondria, and other membrane bound compartments, to establish the optical
454 transparency required for vision. As a result, large regions of the developing and mature lens
455 consist of enucleated cells with minimal intracellular structural landmarks. This biology poses a
456 fundamental limitation for conventional image-based or nucleus-centered segmentation
457 strategies, which typically rely on nuclear staining or organelle boundaries to define individual
458 cells. Consistent with these notions, histological staining of nucleus (Fig. 3A), membrane
459 boundaries (Fig. 3B), Intracellular RNA or protein patterns (Fig. 3C–E) of developing lens in the
460 Xenium mouse pup dataset did not reveal any segmentable information except at the small
461 boundary area where lens differentiation did not start yet or just begun to start. Accordingly, no
462 segmented cells were found in most of the lens area.

463 Nevertheless, the segmentation-independent FICTURE2 inference successfully resolved the
464 spatial transcriptomic architecture underlying lens development and classified the lens fibers into
465 two distinct populations (Fig. 3F). Factor 73 corresponded to the central fibers (Fig. 3G),
466 whereas factor 68 marked fibers located at the peripheral fibers (Fig. 3H). Each factor was

467 supported by a set of specific marker genes that recapitulated their spatial expression patterns.
468 For example, *Cryge* was highly enriched in factor 73 and localized to the center (Fig. 3I),
469 whereas *Mip* was characteristic of factor 68 and predominated in the peripheral fibers (Fig. 3J).

470 Using the ROI function implemented in CartoScope, we further partitioned the lens into three
471 anatomical regions -- core, midzone, and fringe (Fig. 3K) -- and performed differential
472 expression analysis across these regions. ROI based analysis revealed that central core fibers,
473 despite their markedly reduced RNA abundance relative to other regions (Fig. 3C,E), exhibited
474 elevated expression of *Igf2* together with cell death associated genes such as *Fas* and *Pmaip1*
475 (Fig. 3L). This pattern is consistent with a molecular program linked to terminal differentiation
476 and organelle clearance. In contrast, the midzone showed enriched expression of *Alox15*, *Clic5*,
477 *Actn2*, *Trex1*, and *Pacsin3* (Fig. 3M), reflecting an active remodeling program associated with
478 cytoskeletal reorganization and membrane restructuring during fiber elongation. The outermost
479 fringe region displayed higher levels of *Gja8*, *Id2*, *Col6a3*, *Col4a5*, *Col13a1*, *Jag1*, and
480 *Rnaset2a* (Fig. 3N), consistent with ongoing fiber cell differentiation, extracellular matrix
481 organization, and intercellular communication required for lens growth and maturation.

482 Crystallins are the dominant structural proteins of lens fiber cells and are essential for
483 establishing refractive capacity and long-term transparency. Gene level visualization of
484 representative crystallin family members demonstrated marked spatial heterogeneity across the
485 lens (Fig. 3O). For example, *Cryge*, *Crygd* and *Crygb* were enriched toward the central core,
486 whereas *Crygc* and *Crygs* showed relatively stronger signal in the peripheral region. These gene
487 plots indicate that distinct crystallin family members are differentially deployed along the radial
488 axis, reflecting progressive maturation and functional specialization of fiber cells from the
489 equator toward the center.

490 Consistent with these single gene patterns, FICTURE2 factor analysis of crystallin enriched
491 genes revealed two dominant spatial programs in the adult mouse eye Stereo-seq dataset (Fig.
492 3P). One factor, characterized by enrichment of *Crygd*, *Crygb*, *Cryge*, *Crygc*, and *Crygf*, was
493 concentrated in the central lens, whereas the second factor, enriched for *Cryaa*, *Cryba2*, *Crybb2*,
494 *Crybal*, and *Crygs*, predominated in the peripheral region. Direct comparison of *Crygd* and
495 *Crygs* expression further illustrated this spatial segregation, with *Crygd* broadly distributed
496 across the core and *Crygs* preferentially localized toward the outer layers (Fig. 3Q).

497 Overall, segmentation-independent analyses resolved coherent central and peripheral
498 transcriptional programs in both developing and adult lens, despite the absence of segmentable
499 cellular boundaries. These findings demonstrate that biologically meaningful spatial organization
500 can be reconstructed even in tissues composed largely of enucleated cells lacking clear
501 morphological landmarks. By integrating FICTURE2 factor analysis, ROI-based differential
502 expression, and gene-level visualization, CartoScope enables robust characterization of spatial
503 gene expression architecture in highly specialized tissues such as the lens.

504 **Pixel-level inference from both segmentation-dependent and independent analyses**

505 Next, we focused on the portal triad area of MERFISH mouse and Xenium human liver tissues
506 (Fig. S4A-F), where dense arrangement of connective tissue and vasculature, along with
507 heterogeneity in cell shape and size, substantially interfere with segmentation accuracy. Indeed,
508 clustering of segmented cells in both MERFISH and Xenium datasets failed to reveal fine
509 structures underlying the portal triad regions (Fig. S4A,D). However, FICTURE2 can project
510 these clustered cell types into pixel-level (Fig. S4B,E), detailing much finer structure of the
511 portal triad area. Moreover, the segmentation-independent pixel-level factor inference using

512 FICTURE2 (Fig. S4C,F) showed even superior precision in identifying and visualizing critical
513 structures, such as arterial vasculature (dotted circle in Fig. S4C), which was missed in cell-
514 based clustering of the MERFISH dataset (dotted circle in Fig. S4B).

515 Similar comparison was made using Xenium breast cancer dataset (Fig. S4G–X), where default
516 Xenium clustering of segmented cells (Fig. S4H) failed to capture the complexity of underlying
517 tissue histology (Fig. S4G), especially in the tumor stroma area. Although the lack of spatial
518 precision (Fig. S4J) can be alleviated by pixel-level projection of clustered cell types (Fig. S4I),
519 showing finer structure of the stromal cell type (Fig. S4K) in the relevant histological area (Fig.
520 S4L), FICTURE2’s segmentation-independent pixel-level inference (Fig. S4M) identified the
521 diverse transcriptional programs of stromal cells much more comprehensively (Fig. S4N,O).

522 Even pixel-level projection based on cell segmentation could be highly useful. Xenium Ranger’s
523 default cell clustering was already able to identify diverse myeloid cells through cell type
524 clustering (Fig. S4P). However, pixel-level projection of these cell type factors was able to
525 identify many additional cells (Fig. S4Q,R) that are present in the dataset but not detected in the
526 segmentation analysis (Fig. S4P). This could improve, complement, and potentially correct for
527 errors caused by imperfect segmentation. Additional detection of such cell type could be verified
528 by comparing it with histological examination. For instance, focused analysis of a selected
529 region (Fig. S4S–X corresponding to white box in Fig. S4P–R) presents a mast cell cluster
530 identified in an eosinophilic staining in H&E image (Fig. S4V, arrow). But segmentation-based
531 method failed to detect the mast cell transcriptome (Fig. S4S–U) because the mast cell is tiny and
532 its transcripts were mixed with surrounding stromal cells, which failed to make a segment on its
533 own (Fig. S4S). In contrast, pixel-level projection of the cell types identified the missing mast
534 cells (Fig. S4W) in the exactly precise location of where mast cells were identified histologically

535 from the H&E staining (Fig. S4X). These results exemplify the utility of CartoScope in
536 identifying spatial features that were missed and ignored from previous analyses.

537 **Identification and visualization of subcellular transcriptional programs**

538 Through its segmentation-independent factor inference, FICTURE2 can identify subcellular
539 transcriptional programs, and CartoScope is suitable for visualizing and analyzing subcellular
540 factors. In a colon cancer Xenium dataset, 48 factors were identified from segmentation-
541 independent FICTURE2 analysis (Fig. 4A). In colonic crypts which exhibit relatively normal
542 morphology (Fig. 4B), adjacent to the colon adenocarcinoma (white box in Fig. 4A), we were
543 able to identify two distinct factors, one (factor 25) on the apical side and the other (factor 19) on
544 the basolateral side of the crypt (Fig. 4C). The genes constituting factor 25 is mostly related to
545 the pathways for mucus production and secretion, consistent with their apical role of the lumen
546 side of the crypt lining (green in Fig. 4D). In contrast, the genes constituting factor 19 perform
547 various functions in metabolism, redox regulation and immune modulation (red in Fig. 4D). Such
548 observations were not made based on the segmentation-based analyses because the apical factors
549 were located in an area where DAPI signal is absent (Fig. 4E–G), and therefore not represented
550 in the segmentation-based analysis (Fig. 4H).

551 Similar polarized distribution of transcripts at subcellular scale was also observed in the tumor
552 region (Fig. 4I–P). Among the five factors corresponding to the tumor epithelia (factors 0-5 in
553 Fig. 4I), the tumor core area is represented by 3 distinct factors, factors 0, 2 and 4 (Fig. 4J),
554 which exhibits a characteristic subcellular pattern (Fig. 4M–P). Factor 4 occupied the apical-
555 most area (Fig. 4N), while factor 2 is enriched in basal nucleus (Fig. 4P) and factor 0 is
556 widespread across the cytoplasm (Fig. 4O). Even though these three factors belong to the same

557 tumor epithelia, they were so distinct and polarized so that factor 4 and 2 almost never overlaps
558 in the spatial plot (Fig. 4K). One of the most prominent gene constituents of factor 4 is *MAP7*,
559 whose transcripts were localized only in the apical area far from the basally located nucleus (Fig.
560 4L). This is consistent with very recent findings where MAP7 plays an essential role in
561 establishing apical membrane morphology by controlling microtubule dynamics³²; however,
562 localized transcripts which will support localized protein production was not expected
563 previously. These findings exemplify the utility of CartoScope and FICTURE2 to discover
564 known and novel subcellular patterns of transcript localization and potentially inferring their role
565 in tissue dynamics for future research.

566 Likewise, from Xenium spatial data of human pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (Fig. S5A–F),
567 brain glioblastoma (Fig. S5G–L), and ovarian cancer (Fig. S5M–R), CartoScope was able to
568 compare the performance of Xenium Ranger segmented cell clustering (Fig. S5A,G,M), LDA-
569 based segmented cell clustering (Fig. S5C,I,O), their pixel-level projections (Fig. S5B,H,N for
570 Xenium Ranger cluster projection; Fig. S5D,J,P for LDA-based cluster projection), and pixel-
571 level inference (Fig. S5F,L,R), side by side with DAPI histology (Fig. S5E,K,G). The
572 comparison showed that only pixel-level inference (Fig. S5F,L,R) was able to discern the
573 subcellular factors that can isolate tumor cell nucleus from the rest of the cytoplasm, most
574 obviously in the ovarian cancer data (Fig. S5R). CosMx SMI spatial data of human breast cancer
575 (Fig. S5S), prostate cancer (Fig. S5T), and liver cancer (Fig. S5U) also showed that pixel-level
576 inference (right two columns), but not segmentation-based methods (left two columns), were
577 able to isolate subcellular factors that illustrate nuclear-cytoplasmic patterns.

578 **Comprehensive ROI analysis of cell-type-specific differentially expressed genes**

579 A recent study characterized spatial transcriptome of human lung in non-diseased and different
580 stages of pulmonary fibrosis (PF) ³³. Specifically, the study analyzed 10 normal, 15 less affected
581 PF and 20 more affected PF samples in a tissue microarray, analyzed in a single batch of Xenium
582 experiment (Fig. 5A). Through cell segmentation analysis, the original study identified 47
583 clusters of cell types in normal and diseased lung tissues (Fig. 5B). Although these are
584 comprehensive characterization of cell types, their spatial projections do not reveal clear
585 architectural details of the lung tissue under PF (Fig. 5C). Again, pixel-level projections of these
586 cell types using FICTURE2 made the tissue architecture much clearer (Fig. 5D).

587 Using the dataset, we have tested the CartoScope functionalities in performing advanced
588 differential expression analysis. During benchmarking of the brain dataset, we already have
589 shown that CartoScope can perform differential gene expression analysis between defined ROIs
590 (Fig. 1F). Here we show that CartoScope can also perform differential factor analysis (Fig. 5E-I).
591 Using the ROI covering normal lung, less advanced PF and more advanced PF (Fig. 5I), we
592 examined which cell type factors are more represented in normal or PF samples. Normal lung
593 tissues were more enriched in capillary endothelial (Capillary) cells and alveolar type I (AT1)
594 cells (Fig. 5E), while PF tissues were higher in various cell types including B cells, respiratory
595 airway secretory cells (RASC), transitional alveolar type II (AT2) cells (Fig. 5G). Even though
596 normal lung tissue-enriched factors, such as Capillary cells, were relatively lower in PF tissues,
597 they were abundantly found in both normal and PF tissues (Fig. 5E,F). In contrast PF-enriched
598 factors were almost exclusively found in PF tissues (Fig. 5G,H).

599 As substantial area of PF tissues is still covered by endothelial cells, we examined cell-type-
600 specific differential expression analysis, implemented in CartoScope enabled by a few clicks
601 (Fig. 5I). The Capillary-specific differential expression between advanced PF and normal tissue
602 identified that Capillary in PF specifically upregulates *APLN* and *APLNR* genes (Fig. 5J), which
603 are involved in endothelial repair and suppression of endothelial-mesenchymal transition and PF
604 pathogenesis³⁴. Therefore, it is likely that these gene expression changes indicate protective
605 responses of remaining endothelial cells in protecting tissue homeostasis. Spatial gene plotting
606 indeed indicates that *APLNR* is not highly expressed in normal lung (Fig. 5K) but highly
607 expressed in PF lung, specifically in the Capillary cells (Fig. 5L). There are a few areas where
608 extra-endothelial expression of *APLNR* was found; however, plotting all cell type factors
609 identified that those *APLNR* expressions were associated with venous endothelial cells, the
610 related cell type (dotted circles in Fig. 5L–N). Magnification of these *APLNR*-positive
611 endothelial cells indeed confirm that most of the *APLNR* expression is confined within
612 endothelial cell boundaries (Fig. 5O).

613 **Exploring intratumoral heterogeneity with CartoScope**

614 To test the utility of such ROI-based in depth analysis in a single sample, we revisited the human
615 colon cancer dataset that was used for subcellular factoring analysis (Fig. 4). Among the various
616 tumor enriched factors identified from FICTURE2 (Fig. 6A), factors 0 and 3 were concentrated
617 in the tumor core area (Fig. 6B), whereas factors 5 and 6 were found at the lumen surface (Fig.
618 6C). The surface tumor factors were enriched for the cell senescence marker p21 *CDKN1A* and
619 senescence associated inflammatory factors such as *CXCL2* and *CCL20* (Fig. 6D), while
620 expression of these genes was very low in tumor core regions (Fig. 6E). These findings likely
621 reflect activation of distinct transcriptional programs at different sites of the tumor epithelium.

622 The heterogeneity in the tumor epithelial transcriptome may also be associated with changes in
623 the tumor microenvironment. Therefore, to examine potential heterogeneity of the tumor
624 microenvironment, we performed ROI-based differential factor analysis and cell-type-specific
625 differential gene expression analysis as described in Fig. 5. For this purpose, we used a well
626 annotated segmented cell clustering result (Fig. 6F, center), projected it into pixel level data (Fig.
627 6F, left), and segmented the area into three ROIs (Fig. 6F, right) representing tumor surface,
628 tumor core, and adjacent colon. At the factor level, the tumor surface environment was enriched
629 with CD4 positive and proliferating T cells, as well as B cells and monocytes (Fig. 6G), while
630 the adjacent colon environment was enriched with plasma cells (Fig. 6H), and the tumor core
631 environment contained more densely populated epithelial cells (Fig. 6I). Fibroblasts were
632 abundantly observed in all three ROIs (Fig. 6J).

633 Accordingly, we performed fibroblast-specific differential expression analysis restricted to
634 transcript pixels annotated as fibroblasts. This analysis identified numerous genes involved in
635 immune modulation and extracellular matrix remodeling (Fig. 6K), which are key functional
636 features of tumor associated fibroblasts. Notably, two distinct matrix metalloproteinase family
637 members abundantly expressed in fibroblasts emerged as region-specific markers: *MMP12* at the
638 tumor surface (cyan in Fig 6K, left) and *MMP11* in the tumor core (red in Fig. 6K, right). Spatial
639 visualization of these genes (Fig. 6L) demonstrated that neither enzyme was substantially
640 expressed in the lamina propria of the adjacent colon (Fig. 6M). In contrast, *MMP12* was
641 strongly overexpressed in the tumor surface stroma (Fig. 6N), whereas *MMP11* was specifically
642 enriched in the tumor core stroma (Fig. 6O), with expression localized to fibroblast populations.

643 These findings demonstrate that the advanced ROI functions implemented in CartoScope,
644 including differential factor and cell-type-specific differential expression analyses, enable

645 systematic dissection of spatial heterogeneity within complex tissues. Beyond visualizing
646 intratumoral epithelial transcriptome variation, this framework allows coordinated analysis of
647 stromal composition and cell type specific transcriptional programs across defined spatial
648 regions, underscoring its broad utility for integrative spatial transcriptomic studies.

649 **Iterative factor exploration enables biological discovery in the developing growth plate**

650 To illustrate how the CartoScope ecosystem facilitates a virtuous loop — where readily available
651 factors guide annotation, and annotation in turn powers deeper spatial analysis — we examined
652 the growth plate cartilage in the whole embryo Xenium Prime mouse pup dataset. Growth plate
653 chondrocytes are organized along the longitudinal axis, transitioning from resting to
654 proliferative, pre-hypertrophic (maturation), hypertrophic (degeneration) and transitional
655 (calcification) states in structurally zoned patterns, which were well depicted in the FICTURE
656 analysis of the mouse pup dataset (Fig. 7A). Each of the spatial factors representing these states
657 comprises classical markers of chondrocyte zonation, as well as additional markers, which could
658 be retrieved at the bookmark provided in the Figure Legends. Here, we experimentally utilized
659 AI-based cell type annotation using Gemini 3 Flash Preview API by incorporating the prompts
660 suggested by the AnnDictionary software³⁵. While the annotated factors were informative
661 overall, we further refined several annotations to better reflect the underlying biological
662 processes observed in the data. Here, we would focus on two examples demonstrating how fine-
663 grained pixel-level spatial factorization resolves biologically meaningful signals that are
664 otherwise inaccessible.

665 **Resolving osteoclast/chondroclast identity at the chondro-osseous junction**

666 At the terminal hypertrophic zone (referred to calcification zone in Fig. 7A), where cartilage
667 meets the primary spongiosa, chondrocytes are known to undergo either trans-differentiation into
668 osteoblasts or removal by monocyte-lineage cells. Whether these resorptive cells represent true
669 osteoclasts or a functionally distinct chondroclast population has been debated for decades.
670 Although both cell types share monocyte lineage, express TRAP (*Acp5*), and depend on the CSF-
671 1/RANKL pathway³⁶, recent transcriptomic profiling by laser capture microdissection revealed
672 that chondroclasts and osteoclasts are transcriptionally distinct, with chondroclasts enriched for
673 metabolic, ATP synthesis, and proteasome pathways³⁷. Differential MMP expression — notably
674 *Mmp13* enrichment in chondroclasts³⁸ — has also been reported. However, these comparisons
675 have been limited by the difficulty of isolating these sparse cells from their native tissue context,
676 and no study has yet examined them in situ at single-cell resolution using spatial transcriptomics.

677 We asked whether the CartoScope workflow could facilitate identification and spatial
678 comparison of osteoclast-lineage cells within the growth plate. Examination of canonical
679 osteoclast markers *Atp6v0d2*, *Acp5*, *Nfatc1*, *Csflr*, and *Tnfrsf11a* in the Xenium Prime mouse
680 pup dataset revealed individual cells co-expressing all five markers among the dominant
681 *Col10a1*+ hypertrophic chondrocyte population (Fig. 7B). However, cell segmentation-based
682 analyses did not correctly delineate boundaries between the *Col10a1*+ chondrocytes and adjacent
683 osteoclast-lineage cells, and the resulting factor assignments were not biologically coherent (Fig.
684 7C).

685 The CartoScope interface allows users to rapidly evaluate multiple factorization results and
686 assess their validity in a given biological context. In the 192-factor basis, factor 113

687 corresponded to hypertrophic chondrocytes, while factors 48 (monocyte lineage) and 118
688 (osteoclast activity) together captured the osteoclast program. Critically, despite the sparsity of
689 canonical marker transcripts, these factors provided sufficient coverage to identify neighboring
690 cell interactions that neither individual marker genes nor even the union of the five canonical
691 markers could resolve (Fig. 7D). This is because the factorization leverages the full breadth of
692 co-regulated transcriptional programs rather than relying on a small set of known markers. The
693 top 20 genes supporting factor 118 were consistent with known chondroblast/osteoclast activity.
694 Importantly, the factor analysis was able to capture additional moments where hypertrophic
695 chondrocytes were removed by monocyte-osteoclast lineage cells, exemplifying the utility of
696 CartoScope-FICTURE in visualizing critical biological events (Fig. 7D, insets). Beyond the
697 terminal hypertrophic zone, factors 48 and 118 were also detected in the trabecular bone region
698 — where *Col10a1*+ hypertrophic chondrocytes (factor 113) are absent — as well as in periosteal
699 regions, revealing osteoclast activity across multiple tissue compartments within the same
700 section (Fig. 7E).

701 This expanded spatial coverage illustrates how the workflow can facilitate downstream
702 biological inquiry. By comparing factor 118-positive pixels between the trabecular region and
703 the terminal hypertrophic zone (Fig. 7F), we identified genes differentially enriched between
704 these two spatial compartments. There were only three genes which were significantly
705 differentially expressed, and all are MMPs (Fig. 7G). Next to these three genes is *Coll10a*, which
706 is isolated likely because most chondroblast are phagocytosing hypertrophic chondrocytes,
707 abundantly expressing *Coll10a*; however, it did not reach the level of significance. Among the
708 three MMPs identified, *Mmp14* was previously proposed as enriched in chondroblasts relative to
709 osteoclasts^{37,38}. Gene plotting analysis indeed was able to contrast the differing expression levels

710 in osteoclasts in the terminal hypertrophic zone (cyan in Fig. 7F,H) and in the trabecular region
711 (brown in Fig. 7F,H).

712 More broadly, the ability to systematically identify and spatially compare osteoclast-lineage cells
713 across the chondro-osseous junction, periosteum, and trabecular bone within a single tissue
714 section provides a framework for addressing open questions in the field — including the long-
715 standing debate over chondroclast versus osteoclast identity, and the emerging question of
716 whether osteoclasts at different skeletal sites are transcriptionally heterogeneous^{39,40}. These
717 comparisons, which have historically required laborious isolation methods such as laser capture
718 microdissection, become readily accessible through the iterative exploration that the
719 CartoLoader–CartoScope workflow enables.

720 **Cell cycle mapping in the proliferative zone**

721 The proliferative zone of the growth plate illustrates a distinct mode of discovery enabled by the
722 interface. At first inspection, this region appears transcriptionally uninformative because the pan-
723 chondrocyte factor - factor 44 - dominates the signal and obscures finer structure. However,
724 CartoScope allows users to interrogate minor factors that co-occur within the spatial territory of a
725 dominant factor, thereby uncovering more specific transcriptional programs. Using this strategy,
726 we identified two minor factors, factor 22 and factor 30, whose top contributing genes
727 corresponded to established S phase and G2/M phase markers, respectively (Fig. 7I).

728 The spatial distribution of these cell cycle related factors was consistent with known growth plate
729 zonation. S phase and G2/M phase signals were enriched in the proliferative zone, diminished in
730 the pre-hypertrophic zone, and reappeared in the calcification zone, reflecting renewed
731 proliferation associated with endochondral ossification (Fig. 7I). Importantly, these factors were

732 derived from decomposition of the entire embryo section rather than from a growth plate-specific
733 subset, yet they captured cell state programs that are directly informative for growth plate
734 biology.

735 To assess whether these factors faithfully reflect cell cycle state, we examined their distribution
736 within the proliferative zone, where chondrocytes form characteristic columnar - isogenic -
737 structures that arise through clonal expansion. Historically, demonstration of cell cycle
738 synchrony within isogenic columns has required nucleotide incorporation assays. Farnum and
739 Wilsman ⁴¹ used BrdU pulse labeling to show that chondrocytes within a column are more
740 synchronized with each other than with chondrocytes in adjacent columns. More broadly,
741 evaluation of cell cycle dynamics in tissues has relied on nucleotide labeling approaches or
742 dedicated transgenic reporters such as the Fucci system ^{42,43}, neither of which has been
743 systematically applied to growth plate analysis. In our spatial analysis, factors 22 and 30
744 recapitulated these established dynamics without experimental labeling. Within clearly resolved
745 proliferative columns, neighboring cells exhibited concordant cell cycle phase assignments (Fig.
746 7J), consistent with the intra-columnar synchrony previously reported ⁴¹.

747 The gene plotting function of CartoScope provided additional insight into mechanisms of cell
748 cycle regulation across zones. Rapid screening of the seven CDK inhibitors detected in the
749 dataset - *Cdkn1c*, *Cdkn1b*, *Cdkn2c*, *Cdkn2d*, *Cdkn1a*, *Cdkn2a*, and *Cdkn2b* - revealed that two of
750 these inhibitors, *Cdkn1c* (p57Kip2) and *Cdkn1a* (p21), displayed distinct spatial patterns
751 associated with cell cycle arrest (Fig. 7K). Consistent with previous studies linking p57Kip2 to
752 cell cycle exit in hypertrophic chondrocytes ⁴⁴, *Cdkn1c* expression increased markedly in the
753 maturation, or pre-hypertrophic, zone. In contrast, *Cdkn1a* expression was strongly induced in

754 the calcification or transition zone (Fig. 7K,L), suggesting that different regulatory mechanisms
755 govern cell cycle arrest in distinct regions of the growth plate.

756 *Cdkn1a* is a well characterized transcriptional target of the tumor suppressor p53. Notably,
757 additional p53 target genes, including *Mdm2*, *Gadd45a*, and *Sestrins*, as well as pro-apoptotic
758 effectors such as *Pmaip1*, *Bax*, and *Bbc3*, were upregulated in the calcification zone (Fig. 7L).
759 These coordinated expression patterns suggest activation of a p53-mediated program that may
760 contribute to the elimination of hypertrophic chondrocytes prior to their clearance by
761 chondroclasts or osteoclasts.

762 Having validated the biological relevance of these factors against established growth plate
763 biology, this factorization-based framework can serve as a general quantitative tool. It enables
764 direct estimation of proliferative indices from spatial transcriptomic data without transgenic
765 reporters or nucleotide incorporation assays, and it allows systematic comparison of proliferative
766 activity across growth plates within a single tissue section or between distinct regions of the
767 same growth plate.

768

769 **Discussion**

770 Microscopic-resolution spatial transcriptomics and proteomics (μ ST) now enable systematic
771 measurement of molecules in situ at cellular and subcellular resolution, creating unprecedented
772 opportunities to link gene programs to tissue architecture, development, and disease. Yet
773 biological discovery has not kept pace with data generation. We attribute this gap to three
774 interacting bottlenecks.

775 First, μ ST datasets remain fragmented across technologies. Sequencing-based and imaging-based
776 platforms differ in sampling schemes, signal properties, and output formats, which has led to
777 platform-specific preprocessing choices such as grid-based binning or image-driven
778 segmentation. This heterogeneity complicates comparative analysis and prevents routine, parallel
779 processing across studies and platforms.

780 Second, many commonly used analysis strategies often compromise the very resolution that
781 makes μ ST powerful. Grid-based binning can blur fine spatial structure, while cell segmentation
782 depends on imperfect boundary inference that varies across tissues, staining quality, cell density,
783 and sectioning artifacts. In many settings, segmentation introduces contamination or data loss,
784 and it fails precisely in regions where μ ST could be most informative, including crowded niches,
785 multinucleated cells, and compartments where nuclear signal is faint, fragmented, or unreliable.

786 Although segmentation-free factorization and multimodal segmentation methods are emerging,
787 the field lacks a broadly usable, cross-platform ecosystem that harmonizes μ ST datasets and
788 supports analysis at scale.

789 Third, the scale of μ ST data creates a practical access barrier. While raw data are publicly
790 deposited, meaningful exploration typically requires specialized computational expertise,
791 substantial storage, and high-performance computing. As a result, many experimental biologists
792 and biomedical investigators, who are central to hypothesis generation and biological
793 interpretation, are limited to static figures and processed summaries rather than direct, iterative
794 interaction with the primary spatial data.

795 CartoScope was developed to address these bottlenecks through a GIS-inspired, query-driven
796 paradigm for μ ST. Instead of treating each dataset as a monolithic object that must be
797 downloaded, binned, and segmented before use, CartoScope treats histology as a spatial substrate
798 and molecular measurements as aligned, multi-resolution layers that can be streamed on demand.
799 This approach enables seamless navigation from tissue-scale overview to molecular-scale detail
800 while retrieving only the information required for the current view or user-defined region of
801 interest (ROI). The ecosystem integrates three components. CartLoader harmonizes platform
802 outputs into a unified coordinate framework and performs segmentation-independent pixel-level
803 inference using FICTURE2. CartoStore hosts processed datasets and metadata in a cloud-native
804 layout that supports efficient random access. CartoScope provides an interactive web interface
805 for synchronized visualization of histology, genes, inferred factors, and optional segmentation-
806 derived annotations, coupled with ROI-based analyses such as factor enrichment, composition
807 summaries, and differential expression stratified by inferred cell types or spatial context.

808 Across representative applications, CartoScope enabled rapid, reproducible exploration and
809 analysis that would otherwise require substantial custom computation. First, CartoStore's breadth
810 allowed user-driven benchmarking across technologies within shared tissue contexts, revealing
811 practical differences in gene coverage, apparent detection density, and background

812 characteristics. Second, segmentation-independent inference resolved biologically meaningful
813 cell types and transcriptional programs in settings where segmentation was unreliable,
814 exemplified by pancreatic islet subtype structure and by improved visualization of wound-
815 associated senescence programs via pixel-level projections. Third, CartoScope supported
816 subcellular-scale discovery, including polarized programs in colonic crypt epithelium and
817 nuclear-cytoplasmic transcriptome separation in tumors, patterns that are frequently missed by
818 cell-centric analyses. Fourth, CartoScope enabled analysis of tissues with limited segmentable
819 structure, such as the developing and mature lens, where factorization and ROI-based differential
820 expression reconstructed coherent spatial maturation programs despite minimal nuclear
821 landmarks. Fifth, the ROI framework allowed context-aware, cell-type-specific differential
822 expression in disease, illustrated by endothelial programs associated with pulmonary fibrosis.
823 Finally, iterative factor exploration in the growth plate demonstrated how interactive inspection
824 can guide annotation and then enable more targeted spatial comparisons, including osteoclast-
825 lineage heterogeneity at the chondro-osseous junction and spatial mapping of cell cycle states
826 within proliferative columns.

827 A key contribution of CartoScope is that it links exploration, analysis, and communication. The
828 ability to generate persistent bookmarks that capture the full analytical state (view, layers,
829 parameters, and ROIs) allows collaborators and readers to reproduce exact spatial views and
830 extend analyses directly from the browser. In this way, CartoScope supports not only discovery
831 but also transparent reporting and interactive dissemination of spatial results.

832 In summary, CartoScope provides a democratized and scalable ecosystem for harmonized,
833 segmentation-independent μ ST exploration. By combining cross-platform harmonization,
834 efficient pixel-level inference, cloud-optimized multi-resolution data access, and interactive

835 ROI-based analysis, CartoScope reduces the distance between data availability and biological
836 insight. As high-resolution spatial datasets continue to expand in size and diversity, this
837 paradigm offers a practical route toward routine comparative analysis, rapid hypothesis testing,
838 and broader participation in μ ST-driven discovery by both computational and experimental
839 investigators.

840

841 **Code availability**

842 The CartLoader μ ST analysis pipeline is publicly available at
843 <https://github.com/seqscope/cartloader> and documented at <https://seqscope.github.io/cartloader/>.
844 The FICTURE2 software tool is publicly available at <https://github.com/Yichen-Si/punkst> and
845 documented at <https://yichen-si.github.io/punkst/>. The CartoScope is freely accessible at
846 <https://www.cartoscope.app> and documented at <https://seqscope.github.io/cartoscope3o/>.

847 **Data availability**

848 All 320 datasets deposited in CartoScope is publicly available datasets uniformly reprocessed
849 with CartLoader. The original source of each dataset is documented in CartoScope. The
850 reprocessed data is freely accessible at CartoStore, an Open AWS Data Registry available at
851 <https://registry.opendata.aws/cartostore/>. They also can be freely explored interactively through
852 CartoScope. The example input datasets for CartLoader are available at
853 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15759403>. The CartLoader analysis results from each dataset can
854 be accessed at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15759403> (Seq-Scope),
855 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17957312> (Open-ST), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17957307>
856 (STARmap PLUS), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17957309> (Salus-STs),
857 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17957306> (Xenium Prime),
858 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15824955> (Visium HD),
859 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15824967> (Xenium V1),
860 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15824948> (Stereo-seq), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15824938>
861 (Pixel-seq), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15824932> (MERFISH), and
862 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15824926> (CosMx SMI).

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869

870 **Ethics declarations**

871 JHL is an inventor on U.S. Patent No. 12,319,955, filed by The Regents of the University of
872 Michigan, which covers the Seq-Scope method for localized detection of nucleic acids in tissue
873 samples. YH is currently an employee of Samsung Semiconductor. All other authors declare no
874 competing interests.

875

876 **Figure Legends**

877 **Figure 1. CartoScope ecosystem and cross-technology benchmarking in mouse brain.**

878 (A) Schematic overview of the CartoScope ecosystem. Raw microscopic-resolution spatial omics
879 data from imaging-based and sequencing-based platforms are harmonized by CartLoader with
880 segmentation-independent pixel-level inference using FICTURE2, hosted in CartoStore on
881 CORS-enabled cloud storage, and explored through the CartoScope web interface.

882 (B) Representative dataset summary pages displaying harmonized metadata and basic statistics.

883 (C) Cross-technology gene plotting in mouse hippocampus for dentate gyrus markers *Prox1* and
884 *Dcx* and the meningeal marker *Ptgds*.

885 (D) Spatial detection of the choroid plexus marker *Ttr* across sequencing-based platforms.

886 (E) Identification of the CA2 region (dotted circles) using *Ptpn5*, *Pcp4*, and *Rgs14* across
887 datasets.

888 (F) ROI-based differential expression (left) recovers CA2-enriched genes (right) in targeted
889 datasets lacking canonical CA2 markers.

890 Explore the datasets through:

891 <https://main.cartoscope.app/datasets?collections=mouse+brain+collection+across+various+platfo>

892 [rms](#) (All)

893

894 **Figure S1. Cross-technology comparison based on segmentation-independent factor**
895 **inference in testis and kidney**

896 (A) Mouse testis datasets profiled by Seq-Scope, Stereo-seq, and Salus-STS, visualized in
897 CartoScope for FICTURE2-based factor inference. Insets indicate zoomed regions highlighting
898 seminiferous tubule organization.

899 (B) Mouse kidney datasets generated by Visium HD (probe-based), Stereo-seq, and SeqFISH+,
900 visualized by factor inference with corresponding magnified regions.

901 (C) Human kidney Xenium dataset (V1). Comparison of segmentation-independent factor
902 inference, Xenium Ranger segmented cell clustering, and pixel-level projection of segmented
903 clusters, with H&E reference.

904 (D) Human kidney Visium HD dataset. Factor inference and Space Ranger segmented cell
905 clustering compared with matched H&E image.

906 Boxed areas are magnified either right or bottom as indicated in arrows.

907 Explore the datasets through:

908 <https://main.cartoscope.app/datasets?collections=mouse+testis+whole+transcriptome+datasets>

909 (All)

910

911 **Figure 2. Segmentation-independent pixel-level inference resolves pancreatic islet subtypes**
912 **and wound-associated programs**

913 (A–F) Human pancreas Xenium dataset. Comparison of Xenium Ranger cell clustering (A),
914 LDA-based cell clustering (B), FICTURE2 pixel-level factors (C), islet-restricted factors (D),
915 and corresponding DAPI overlays (E,F).

916 (G–L) Individual FICTURE2 factors corresponding to pancreatic islet subtypes: beta (*INS*),
917 alpha (*GCG*), CPHN (*CHGA*), delta (*SST*), gamma (*PPY*), and epsilon (*GHRL*).

918 (M–R) Gene plotting of *INS*, *GCG*, *CHGA*, *SST*, *PPY*, and *GHRL* confirms correspondence
919 between marker expression and inferred factors.

920 (S–T) Human skin Xenium dataset. Comparison of Xenium Ranger cell clustering and pixel-
921 level projection of clustered cell types in wounded skin.

922 (U–V) Gene plotting of senescence markers *CDKN1A* (p21) and *CDKN2A* (p16) over
923 FICTURE2 factor background in control and wounded skin.

924 (W) Selected FICTURE2 factors in wounded skin highlighting spatial organization of injury-
925 associated cell populations.

926 Explore the datasets through:

927 <https://main.cartoscope.app/dataset?bookmark=a002d2be-4fc5-42a5-9893-6e847b7b5d9b> (A–R)

928 <https://main.cartoscope.app/dataset?bookmark=290e5214-20ec-40cf-95ec-90d8eec6401e> (S–W)

929

930 **Figure S2. Segmentation-independent factor inference in CosMx human pancreas datasets**

931 (A–C) Human pancreas CosMx Spatial Touchstone dataset (1,000 genes). Comparison of
932 Xenium Ranger cell clustering (A), pixel-level projection of clustered cells (B), and FICTURE2
933 pixel-level factors (C).

934 (D–F) FICTURE2 factors resolving beta and alpha/delta islet populations.

935 (G–I) Gene plotting of *INS*, *GCG*, and *SST* confirms correspondence between marker expression
936 and inferred factors.

937 (J–N) Human pancreas CosMx sample dataset (18,996 genes) generated by Nanostring.
938 Comparison of segmentation-based clustering (J–K) and FICTURE2 factor inference (L–N). Box
939 in (M) is magnified in (N).

940 (O) Islet subtype visualization showing islet populations expressing different hormones through
941 a gene plotting analysis.

942 Explore the datasets through:

943 <https://main.cartoscope.app/dataset?bookmark=c147f310-7d06-4fb4-b514-86a92e854397> (A–I)

944 <https://main.cartoscope.app/dataset?bookmark=00e8b9e8-6ee4-4a64-aa62-dae9f07e43a6> (J–O)

945

946

947 **Figure S3. Harmonized analysis of lymphoid organ transcriptomic and proteomic datasets**

948 (A) Human tonsil Visium HD dataset showing FICTURE2 pixel-level factors with and without
949 H&E reference; segmentation information not available.

950 (B) Human tonsil Xenium V1 dataset comparing FICTURE2 pixel-level factors, Xenium Ranger
951 segmentation, and pixel-level projection.

952 (C–E) Human lymph node datasets (Visium HD, Xenium V1, Xenium 5K) visualized by
953 FICTURE2, with comparison to segmentation and projection where available.

954 (F–G) Seq-Scope-X spatial proteomics datasets (TotalSeq-A) from human tonsil (F) and mouse
955 spleen (G) analyzed using FICTURE2 pixel-level factor inference.

956 (H–I) CODEX spatial proteomics datasets from human lymph node (H) and spleen (I) showing
957 FICTURE2-derived factors.

958 (J–K) Singular G4X multi-omics transcriptome data from human tonsil comparing FICTURE2
959 (J), segmentation, and projection (K) analyses.

960 (L) Singular G4X proteomic channels (CD4, CD8, CD20, CD11c, CD31, Ki67, PanCK, aSMA).

961 Boxed areas are magnified either right or bottom as indicated in arrows.

962 Explore the datasets through:

963 <https://main.cartoscope.app/datasets?collections=lymphoid+organ+collection> (All)

964

965 **Figure 3. Segmentation-independent reconstruction of spatial programs during lens**
966 **development**

967 (A–E) Xenium mouse pup lens dataset showing DAPI (A), cell boundary staining (B),
968 intracellular RNA (C), intracellular protein (D), and transcriptome density (E), illustrating the
969 lack of segmentable structure in most lens regions.

970 (F) FICTURE2 pixel-level factor map of the lens.

971 (G–J) Two dominant lens fiber factors identified by FICTURE2. Factor 73 marks central fibers
972 (G) and factor 68 marks peripheral fibers (H), with corresponding gene plots of representative
973 marker genes (I–J).

974 (K) ROI partitioning of the lens into core, midzone, and fringe regions.

975 (L–N) ROI-based gene plotting highlighting central (L), midzone (M), and fringe (N)-enriched
976 markers.

977 (O) Spatial distribution of representative crystallin genes across the developing lens.

978 (P–Q) Adult mouse eye Stereo-seq dataset showing crystallin-enriched FICTURE2 factors (P)
979 and differential localization of *Crygd* and *Crygs* along the radial axis (Q).

980 Explore the datasets through:

981 <https://main.cartoscope.app/dataset?bookmark=eb153ba3-562d-4d79-9e1c-052f3a3c33a9> (A–O)

982 <https://main.cartoscope.app/dataset?bookmark=e10d4df9-b90c-4c17-abc7-760d2087654f> (P–Q)

983

984 **Figure S4. Pixel-level projection and segmentation-independent inference improve**
985 **structural resolution in liver and breast cancer**

986 (A–C) MERFISH mouse liver portal triad region showing default segmentation (A), pixel-level
987 projection of segmented clusters using FICTURE2 (B), and segmentation-independent
988 FICTURE2 pixel-level factors (C).

989 (D–F) Xenium human liver portal triad region comparing Xenium Ranger segmentation (D),
990 pixel-level projection (E), and FICTURE2 pixel-level factors (F).

991 (G–O) Xenium human breast cancer dataset. Comparison of H&E (G), segmentation (H,J), pixel-
992 level projection (I,K), and FICTURE2 pixel-level factors (M), with stromal factors highlighted
993 alone (N) and overlaid with H&E (O).

994 (P–R) Myeloid cell populations identified by Xenium Ranger clustering (P) and enhanced by
995 pixel-level projection with (R) and without H&E overlay (Q). Boxed regions indicate areas
996 shown at higher magnification in (S–X).

997 (S–X) High-magnification views of boxed regions in (P–R) illustrating mast cells missed by
998 segmentation (S–U) but detected by pixel-level projection (W,X), aligned with H&E (V).

999 Explore the datasets through:

1000 <https://main.cartoscope.app/dataset?bookmark=2432a6b0-8e73-4016-9af5-ec5b7b47b183> (A–C)

1001 <https://main.cartoscope.app/dataset?bookmark=6af4fb8e-da3f-459e-ac45-37bd1800a376> (D–F)

1002 <https://main.cartoscope.app/dataset?bookmark=ba22e532-7035-43ef-8c16-c2f3bbe9f8bd> (J–R)

1003 <https://main.cartoscope.app/dataset?bookmark=77ac456e-e56f-4605-9564-2815c0f625e6> (S–X)

1004 **Figure 4. Identification and visualization of subcellular transcriptional programs in colon**
1005 **cancer**

1006 (A–D) SPATCH colon cancer Xenium 5K dataset. FICTURE2 pixel-level factors (A)
1007 highlighting normal colonic crypt organization (B, boxed in A) and separation of apical and
1008 basolateral transcriptional programs (C), with DAPI and gene group overlays (D).

1009 (E–H) Comparison of DAPI (G), FICTURE2 normal colon factors (E,F), and Xenium default
1010 segmentation (H), illustrating loss of apical signals in segmentation-based analysis.

1011 (I–L) Tumor epithelial factors identified by FICTURE2 (I). Selected subcellular factors reveal
1012 polarized programs within tumor epithelium (J,K), with MAP7 gene plotting showing apical
1013 transcript localization (L).

1014 (M–P) High-magnification views of tumor regions (M) showing distinct apical (N), basal nuclear
1015 (P), and cytoplasmic (O) subcellular factors, with DAPI overlays confirming spatial
1016 organization.

1017 Boxed areas are magnified either right or bottom as indicated in arrows.

1018 Explore the datasets through:

1019 <https://main.cartoscope.app/dataset?bookmark=3eddc05-538d-4108-8635-e6aceal86da4> (A–H)

1020 <https://main.cartoscope.app/dataset?bookmark=0063b7dd-72f2-4127-83c9-eb96f22131c8> (I–P)

1021

1022 **Figure S5. Comparison of segmentation-based clustering, pixel-level projection, and**
1023 **segmentation-independent factor inference across cancer datasets**

1024 (A–R) Xenium human pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (A–F), brain glioblastoma (G–L), and
1025 ovarian cancer (M–R) datasets. Comparison of Xenium Ranger cell clustering (A,G,M) and its
1026 pixel-level projection (B,H,N), LDA-based clustering (C,I,O) and its pixel-level projection
1027 (D,J,P), DAPI (E,K,G), and FICTURE2 pixel-level factors (F,L,R).

1028 (S–U) CosMx human breast cancer (S), prostate cancer (T) and liver cancer (U) datasets
1029 comparing segmentation-based clustering (first column), pixel-level projection (second column),
1030 and FICTURE2 pixel-level factors (third column, magnified in fourth).

1031 Explore the datasets through:

1032 <https://main.cartoscope.app/dataset?bookmark=38cf7648-d1f7-424a-801f-f6c66699856b> (A–F)

1033 <https://main.cartoscope.app/dataset?bookmark=25042119-f69f-4534-8727-ebbf640796b8> (G–L)

1034 <https://main.cartoscope.app/dataset?bookmark=cf25e8c4-0a68-474f-9c47-99cac33b9dad> (M–R)

1035 <https://main.cartoscope.app/dataset?bookmark=0137d064-faa6-43fd-ada3-20876f92fe45> (S)

1036 <https://main.cartoscope.app/dataset?bookmark=ec33b02a-3076-4c33-b3d8-b3c41d1a4cc8> (T)

1037 <https://main.cartoscope.app/dataset?bookmark=dd2471a8-a07a-4f35-a2a0-96f3ce7d2998> (U)

1038

1039 **Figure 5. ROI-based factor and cell-type-specific differential expression analysis in**
1040 **pulmonary fibrosis**

1041 (A) Overview of Xenium lung tissue microarray samples spanning unaffected and pulmonary
1042 fibrosis conditions.

1043 (B) Cell cluster annotations identified from the Xenium Ranger segmented cell analysis.

1044 (C–D) Comparison of Xenium Ranger clustering (C) and pixel-level projection of clustered cells
1045 (D) in more affected pulmonary fibrosis regions. Boxed areas are magnified to the right.

1046 (E–H) Differential factor analysis identifying normal-enriched (E,F) and pulmonary fibrosis-
1047 enriched (G,H) factors. Boxed areas are magnified in the right panel with corresponding colors.

1048 (I) ROI definition for unaffected, less affected, and more affected regions used for downstream
1049 analysis.

1050 (J) Capillary-specific differential expression analysis between unaffected and more affected
1051 regions.

1052 (K–O) Gene plotting of *APLNR* in unaffected (K) and more affected (L–O) regions, overlaid
1053 with Capillary factor (K,L,O), all factors (M) and Capillary and Venous factors (N). Boxed areas
1054 in (L) are magnified in (O) with corresponding colors.

1055 Explore the datasets through:

1056 <https://main.cartoscope.app/dataset?bookmark=839d90c6-d4c3-42f6-a683-d4fc24e7f4f1> (All)

1057 <https://main.cartoscope.app/dataset?bookmark=ee3f543d-bb9d-4d11-8de4-26eb03981e97> (C,D)

1058 <https://main.cartoscope.app/dataset?bookmark=6e076bf8-f735-4ca2-ab69-9224c3426146> (K–O)

1059 **Figure 6. ROI-based dissection of intratumoral heterogeneity in colon cancer**

1060 (A–E) SPATCH colon cancer Xenium 5K dataset showing FICTURE2 pixel-level factors across
1061 tumor and adjacent colon. Tumor core-enriched factors (B) and tumor surface-enriched factors
1062 (C) are shown separately. Lists of top enriched genes for representative tumor core-associated
1063 factor 0 (top) and tumor surface-associated factor 6 (bottom) are shown (D). Gene plotting of
1064 tumor surface-associated genes, including *CDKN1A*, *CXCL2*, and *CCL20*, is shown (E). Boxed
1065 areas are magnified to the right in panels with corresponding colors.

1066 (F) Xenium Ranger segmentation-based results (left) with annotated cell types (right). ROI area
1067 selection defining tumor surface (yellow), tumor core (cyan), and adjacent colon (blue) for
1068 downstream analysis.

1069 (G–J) ROI-based differential factor analysis identifying tumor surface-enriched (G), adjacent
1070 colon-enriched (H), tumor core-enriched (I), and universally detected (J) factors across regions.

1071 (K) Fibroblast-specific differential expression analysis comparing tumor surface and tumor core
1072 regions.

1073 (L–O) Gene plotting illustrating region-specific fibroblast expression patterns (L), including
1074 *MMP12* enrichment in tumor surface stroma (N) and *MMP11* enrichment in tumor core stroma
1075 (O), with minimal expression in adjacent colon (M).

1076 Explore the dataset through:

1077 <https://main.cartoscope.app/dataset?bookmark=8c9c4d10-5589-4496-ad51-429a8f532bcc> (All)

1078

1079 **Figure 7. Iterative factor exploration reveals osteoclast heterogeneity and cell cycle**
1080 **dynamics in the growth plate**

1081 (A) Whole embryo Xenium Prime mouse pup dataset showing FICTURE2 pixel-level factors
1082 across growth plate zones, including resting, proliferative, maturation, hypertrophic,
1083 calcification, and metaphyseal regions.

1084 (B–D) Identification of osteoclast-lineage cells at the chondro-osseous junction. Co-expression
1085 of canonical osteoclast markers (B), segmentation-based clustering (C), and FICTURE2 pixel-
1086 level factors resolving hypertrophic chondrocytes and osteoclast-lineage programs (D) are
1087 shown. Boxed areas, representing osteoclasts phagocytosis of hypertrophic chondrocytes, are
1088 magnified in insets.

1089 (E–H) Spatial comparison of osteoclast-lineage factors (E) between calcification zone, periosteal
1090 region, and trabecular bone. ROI selection is shown (F), differential gene analysis specific to
1091 osteoclast factor (factor 118) between regions is shown (G), and representative gene plotting
1092 illustrating differential *Mmp14* expression is shown (H). Boxed area in (E) corresponds to the
1093 area in (B–D).

1094 (I) Proliferative zone showing minor cell cycle-associated factors corresponding to S phase and
1095 G2/M phase within the dominant chondrocyte background. Boxed area is magnified in (J).

1096 (J) High-magnification view of proliferative columns demonstrating intra-columnar synchrony of
1097 cell cycle phase assignments.

1098 (K) Gene plotting of *Cdkn1c* and *Cdkn1a* across growth plate zones.

1099 (L) Gene plotting of p53 target and apoptosis-associated genes enriched in the calcification zone.

1100 Grey background corresponds to spatial gene expression density map.

1101 Explore the dataset through:

1102 <https://main.cartoscope.app/dataset?bookmark=7e1082e1-79c6-4288-b02f-de7913730e38> (All)

1103

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Human Pancreas Xenium Dataset

Human Skin Xenium Dataset

Human Pancreas CosMx Spatial Touchstone Dataset (1,000 genes): Multi-Sample Analysis

Human Pancreas CosMx Sample Dataset (18,996 genes)

SPATCH Colon Cancer Xenium 5K Data

Xenium Human Pancreatic Ductal Adenocarcinoma Data

Xenium Human Brain Glioblastoma Data

Xenium Human Ovarian Cancer Data

S CosMx Human Breast Cancer Data

T CosMx Human Prostate Cancer Data

U CosMx Human Liver Cancer Data

